

Subject: Political Science**LYCEUM INDIA****Title: Problems and Prospects of Agrarian Society:
A Special Reference to Farmers of Odisha****Journal of Social Sciences****Author: Ajit Barik
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D.B. Degree College, Bhatli****Abstract:** One of the most serious challenges of our society is agrarian issues. Politically every year new farmer welfare schemes are introduced but the real problems of farmers are unsolved till now. The high price rates of agricultural products in markets, increasing numbers of farmer suicides, increasing numbers of unemployment in rural areas, lack of interest among farmers for cultivation are the reflection of agrarian problems. In an era of globalization, the income of farmers is unsatisfactory due to several reasons. This research article study about the different problems of farmers especially of Odisha.**Keywords:** Agrarian issues, Agricultural products, farmer suicides, unemployment, globalization.**Introduction:**

Odisha is an Agrarian state of Eastern coastal India. It is India's ninth largest state by area. according to the 2011 census, it has a geographical area of 1,55,707 km and a population of 4.19 crores. Agriculture is the prime source of state economy and lively hood of rural people. Agriculture and husbandry sector contribute more than 23.43 % of Net State Domestic Product (NSDP) and provides employment, direct or indirect to 65% of its population. Hence agriculture plays a critical role in the economy of state. On the basis of topography, climate and soil types the state is divided into 10 agro climatic zones. The annual normal rain fall of the state is 1451.2 mms of which monsoon rainfall (June to September) is 1144.3 mms i.e. 79% of total rainfall. The climate of the state is tropical characterized by high temperature, high humidity, medium to high rainfall and mild winters. The kharif paddy is the main crop of the state of Odisha. Most of the paddy area cultivated under un-irrigated conditions during kharif session. Hence the food grain production in Odisha almost depends upon weather conditions and rainfall during kharif season. Odisha is one of the poorest states with 83% of population living in rural areas. furthermore, rural poverty accounts for 91% of poverty in state, with 36% of the rural population living in poverty, agriculture employs more than 60% of the population and rice is the state's primary crop. In Odisha agriculture is characterized by low productivity due to a variety of factors like natural calamities, lack of proper irrigation facilities, climate conditions, lack of proper market system and labour shortage for cultivation etc. Although the government of India and the state government of Odisha started various schemes for farmers these are inadequate to overcome the real problems of agrarian society of Odisha.

AGRARIAN PROBLEMS**1. Natural Calamities -**

As a coastal state Odisha is one of the most vulnerable states in India affected by natural disasters. More or less every year drought, flood, and cyclones are the most common natural calamities that breaks the backbone of farmers economic conditions.

A. Cyclones- Odisha is more prone area of cyclone than other coastal states in India, with about one third of cyclones in the east coast making rainfall in the state between the month May to October. The districts of Balasore, Bhadrak, Jajpur, Cuttuck, Puri, Ganjam, Kendrapada, Jagatsingpur, Khorda and Gajapati are

particularly vulnerable. During Cyclone fani the state government estimated that more than 30% of crops were damaged in Odisha, with over 100,000 hectares of agricultural land affected in 14 districts. Bulbul affected around 300,000 hectares of agricultural land. The cyclone Yaas affected 5,700 hectares of agricultural land of odisha.

B. Drought- Drought is another natural calamity which affect to the cultivation of odisha. many subdivisions of western Odisha especially Padampur, Bolangir , Nuapada , Khariar, Bhabanipatna , and Phulbani are the major drought prone area where 47 blocs are affected area of low rainfall . Records reaveal that there were droughts in 1841-42, 1942-43, 1849-50, 1850-51, 1954-55, 1965,1966, 1967, 1979,1984, 2000,2002,2003. In the annals of history, the devastating famine of 1867 which is known as ‘Na Anka Durbhikhya’ was mainly because of extensive drought.

C. Flood- Rivers are flow like Artery on the main land of odisha. Important rivers such as the Mahanadi, Subarnarekha, Bramhani, Baitarani, Rusikulya, Vansadhara and there many tributaries and branches flowing through the state expose vast areas to floods every year. But damages are caused due to floods mainly in the Mahanadi, the Bramhani and Baitarani. Due to heavy rainfall in these rivers the large areas of paddy cultivation damages and it brought challenges for farmers.

2. Lack of proper market system and cold storage

The improper market system leads to agrarian issues. The farmers of Odisha faced the diversity of problems of market system in their local area. As per the study, absence of organized marketing institutions, lack of sound market infrastructure, lack of cold storage space, lack of knowledge on proper marketing system of paddy crups, non-receipt of immediate payment, traditional system of storage system and expensive transporting system are the main problems of agriculture. The procedure of paddy marketing system is also very complex. Due to complexity of Mandi system in Odisha many farmers are directly selling their paddy to private paddy seeds company of western Odisha especially in Bargarh district. The government of Odisha only buy a part of farmers production of paddy and rest remained unsold.

3. Labour shortage in cultivations

Labour scarcity in agriculture is a prime issue of agrarian society. In Odisha the seasonal nature of the agriculture leads to labour scarcity. In agricultural field workers work for only few months in a year that’s why they start looking for permanent’s jobs and regular income. The non -agricultural industries like construction works, small food industries and others local factories jobs provide some good wages compare to agricultural sector. The rural youths they start to move from village to township for their better livelihood and good earnings. Apart from this the governmental schemes like MGNREGA (Mahatma Gandhi National Rural employment Guarantee Act), 2005 attracts to workers of rural area because of high wages. Some rural people of western Odisha they migrated towards other states as industrial workers. the issue of labour migration started after the festival of ‘Nuakhai’ (The mass festival of western Odisha). some rural workers are also engaged in ‘Ita Bhati’ (bricks making). So, the labour problems are unsolved in cultivation.

SCHEMES FOR FARMERS

1. Centrally sponsored schemes-

A. National food security mission (NFSM)

The scheme is being implemented from 2007-08 as a centrally sponsored scheme with an objective to enhance the production and productivity of rice and pulse crops in selected districts of the state in mission mode.

B. National mission for sustainable Agriculture (NMSA)

The scheme is being implemented with different components viz. Soil Health Management (SHM), soil health card, Paramparagat Krishi Vikas Yojana (PKVY) and Bharatiya Prakrutik Krisi Pahari (BPKP). The above schemes are provided for agricultural development of farmers.

C. Pradhan Mantri Krishi Sinchai Yojana (PMKSY)

This scheme aims at providing irrigation facilities to all the farmers of India (Har Khet Ko Pani) and increasing the water use efficiency of agriculture (Per Drop More Crop).

D. Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana (PMFBY)

The PMFBY launched on 18th February 2016 by the Prime Minister Sri Narendra Modi. this scheme is an insurance service for farmers for their yields. It was formulated in line with one nation one scheme.

2. State sponsored schemes-

The state government of Odisha has several schemes in recent years.

A. Krushak Assistance for Livelihood and Income Augmentation (KALIA)

The KALIA scheme was introduced in 2018 to support small marginal farmers as well as landless agricultural households. It is considered one of the first Universal Basic income (UBI) Scheme in India.

B. DBT Farm mechanization scheme

This scheme allows qualified farmers to buy agricultural machinery equipment's or tools once in their lifetime. The agriculture and farmers department have a DBT cell that works with banks to offer interest-free loans and subsidies to help farmers with initial payments.

C. Bhumihina Agriculturalists Loan and Resources Augmentation Model (BALARAM)

Under the BALARAM scheme, the government of Odisha has a set target to provide farm loans to 7 lakhs landless farmers. this scheme is also a popular farmer welfare scheme of Odisha government in recent time.

RECOMMENDATION AND CONCLUSION

The above discussion makes it clear that the problems of agrarian society is very complex. Although both the central and states governments schemes are implementing in Odisha for agricultural development the outcome of these schemes are limited. There are requirements of large investment in agriculture and its allied sectors, including irrigation, easy transport system for agricultural products, rural infrastructure and establishment of new rural markets, farm research etc. If, in Odisha the different welfare schemes like public distribution system, midday meals for school children, rural health insurance and integrated child development scheme successfully implemented than the agrarian economy of Odisha will be benefitted indirectly. There should be need of proper monitoring system of crops failure due to natural calamities by the local authorities. There is need of different training programmes for farmers about the modern technology of agriculture in time to time. Authentic weather information should be given to farmers for managing water irrigation in cultivation. Special governmental subsidies can be providing for agricultural equipment's in rural areas for the modern agriculture. Government should be taking the initiative for proper market regulation. The market system for paddy crops will be easy.

Increasing population of India require huge food production in present scenario. A proper sustainable system of agriculture can be able to fulfil the demand of the time. It was said that agriculture is not only the backbone of Indian economy but also associated with the culture of India. Different festivals of our culture relating to agriculture are associated with Laxmi, the goddess of prosperity and wealth which suggests that the Indian culture can only be enriched by attaching importance to agriculture.

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